

ECHOES OF THE CITY: THE URBAN ENVIRONMENTAL PROBLEM IN THE MOSSOROENSE CAPITAL THROUGH HISTORICAL GEOGRAPHY

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Abstract: The municipality of Mossoró has a history of floods and floods resulting from the occupation of its floodplains, a dynamic that reflects the society-nature conflict inherent to ecological imbalances conceived from the dialogue with the social theory of the disease as urban environmental problems. In this perspective, the objective of this work is to understand the insertion of water bodies in the conformation of territorial diseases of mossoroense urban space. For this purpose, bibliographic and documentary research was used. Among the consulted authors are: Santos (1988; 2012), Harley (1991), Worster (1991), Cronon (1996), Freitas (2005), Fialho (2007), Novaes and Palacios (2015), among others. Empirical material is official data and documents published by IBGE, the Municipality of Mossoró and the Public Prosecutor's Office of Rio Grande do Norte. The results show that water bodies become part of urban environmental issues with the population increase and the resulting pressure on these resources for supply and economic development. It is observed that, throughout its constitution as a city, Mossoroense society ceases to have a harmonious relationship with the Apodi-Mossoró River by appropriating the available natural resources in a utilitarian way, generating the contamination of the water table and the disappearance of several watercourses .

Keywords: Water irregularity. Urban interventions. Historical cartography.

INTRODUCTION

Like so many other cities, the occupation of Mossoró is linked to a river plain, more specifically, that of the Apodi-Mossoró river, which over time has put the sustainability of water resources in the region at risk. The proximity to this body of water allowed the population to settle down and later develop economic activities despite the irregular rainfall that characterizes the municipality, transforming the way Mossoroenses related to the environment.

Urban interventions become part of the agenda of local managers, many of which are specifically directed to the Mossoró River. Imbalances begin to emerge associated with urban expansion, triggering environmental problems that over the years conform "roughness" in the urban space. That is, forms that remain from the past, resulting "from the process of suppression, accumulation, superposition, with which things are replaced and accumulated everywhere" (SANTOS, 2012, p. 140).

At the same time, under the prism of the *social theory of illness*, at urban environmental conditions are considered responsible for diseases, especially epidemic outbreaks (FERREIRA *et al.*, 2008). Thus, when we transpose the precepts of this theory, which originated numerous topographies and medical geographies, to the environmental plane itself, urban environmental problems can be considered territorial "diseases", bearing in mind that they are characterized as an imbalance, a fragility resulting from human action on the environment.

Referring to Santos (2012), we consider environmental imbalances as roughness, processes arising from past crystallizations that blend into the present landscape. It is believed that, in the process of constituting the urban space, Mossoró society lost its balanced relationship with the Apodi-Mossoró river, appropriating the available natural resources in a utilitarian way. This process caused the degradation of groundwater and the suppression of water bodies that are important for maintaining a healthy environment. Thus, our research problem starts from the following question: How were the lakes and rivers appropriated throughout the growth of the city of Mossoró?

The general objective of the research is, therefore, to understand the insertion of water bodies in the formation of territorial "diseases" in the city's urban space. Therefore, we seek to analyze the impact of the city's urban expansion process on anthropic actions around the Apodi-Mossoró river; identify the role of associated events in the composition of territorial "diseases"; and to verify the incidence of events identified in contemporary urban issues in the clipping on screen.

In general terms, the research is justified by the need to reflect on the consequences of the conformation of cities, inspiring studies on the development of more positive economic, social and environmental relations. That said, the present work first exposes the methodological procedures followed for the development of the research. Then, we expose the discussion proposed from the topics: "The contribution of Historical Cartography to the understanding of urban environmental problems" and "The territorial 'illnesses' of Mossoró city: dialoguing with past cartographic products", finally, we weave our "Final Considerations".

Methodological path: meaning the route taken

The methodological procedures adopted were bibliographical and documentary research. In the first moment we have the literature review for the construction of the theoretical-methodological foundation of the study. Among the references that are part of our construct are: in the interface Geography, Historical Geography-Environmental History works that deal with research in Environmental History, with authors such as Worster (1991) and Pádua (2010) to guide our way ; Freitas (2005) on the relationship between Environmental History and Geography; and Santos (1988; 1997; 2012) with the concepts of landscape and roughness.

With regard to Historical Cartography, the following were important: Harley (1991), Fialho (2007) and Teixeira (2016) discussing historical urban cartography; Andrade (2013) Historical Cartography as an instrument for analyzing past spatial configurations; and Novaes and Palacios (2015) the definition of Historical Cartography.

In the urban environmental dimension, reference was made to: Rodrigues (1997) and the methodological propositions on the urban environmental issue and Tucci (2003; 2008) in his reflections on urban flooding.

Based on the reflections provided by these authors, our theoretical construction is based on the premise that the interdisciplinarity inherent in geographic science allows us to dialogue with different areas of knowledge, contributing to studies on geographic space and the society-nature relationship. One of these dialogues develops with History, forged in the dialectic between action and structure that results in Historical Geography.

The communion between Historical Geography and Environmental History materializes, above all, in the investigation of environmental issues that affect contemporary society (FREITAS, 2005) . Environmental History is the study of interactions between human cultures and nature through time, examining how the environment influences the historical process, and how people reorganize and transform it using technology. . 311).

Santos (1988) and Worster (1991) consider the natural environment to be increasingly artificial, impregnated with territorial prostheses that mischaracterize what we conceive as first nature. This second nature, the result of human intentionality, presents disharmonious environmental conditions inherent to urban living and doing (CRONON, 1996), colluding with the adoption of a conception of nature as a hostile element (SANTOS, 1988).

Although we agree with Freitas (2005) about the need for this cooperation to deal with the complexity of the geographic space and the problems inherent to it, we added the interface Historical Geography-Environmental History, Historical Cartography. By using Geography,

History and Cartography, we seek to understand the environmental issues of Mossoró city through the landscape, apprehended as an artifact and as a system (SANTOS, 1988) from past cartographic elaborations. The landscape and graphic representations have a technical dimension that gives meaning to the set of elements/objects interconnected in their conformation, facilitating a spatial understanding of objects, concepts, conditions, processes and facts linked to a specific space-time context (HARLEY, 1991).

Authors such as Silva (1983), Felipe (2001), Pinheiro (2006; 2008), Cascudo (2010), Souza (2010) and Oliveira (2011) were used to understand the process of formation and urban expansion of Mossoró. .

In empirical research, we raised documents, cartographic and statistical materials to subsidize the process of comparative analysis of the urban environmental dimension in the municipality. The main sources used were the official publications of the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE) – population data (1980-2021) and cartographic bases (2020 territorial grids); of the Municipality of Mossoró – Code of Works, Positions and Buildings of the Municipality (1855; 1966; 1975; 1989; 2001 and 2010); of the Public Ministry of Rio Grande do Norte - Official State Gazette (2021) and urban cartographic representations, namely:

- AP lanta from the City of Mossoró/Dr. Gustavo LG Dodt, inspector. Esc. Original 1: 500 – Assu (RN)- [sn], 12/26/1879. 1 Plant MS. Color; 29x29cm. Rep. Telegraph General. Archives of the Secretariat of Drawings.
- The cartographic representation of Uma Tentativa de Mossoró Seen in 1883 in the work of Raimundo Nonato da Silva (Urbanistic Evolution of Mossoró);
- The Topographic Plan of the Central Region of Mossoró, 1926, prepared by Francisco Alves Maia. Urban survey requested by intendant Hemetério Fernandez de Queiroz during the administration of Rodolfo Fernandes; and
- The Sanitation and Water Supply Plant of Mossoró, designed on a scale of 1:50,000 by the Saturnino de Brito Office in 1953.

THE CONTRIBUTION OF HISTORICAL CARTOGRAPHY TO THE UNDERSTANDING OF URBAN ENVIRONMENTAL PROBLEMS

Historical studies on the city cover a range of themes that pervade modernization, reforms and urban transformations. In this sense, environmental issues play an important role in the construction of modern thought. The territorialization of society through the construction

of concrete environments in continuous interaction with the natural environment made the understanding of this space an intrinsic element of social existence itself (PÁDUA, 2010, p. 82-83).

Still,

It is not a question of reducing historical analysis to the biophysical, as if this aspect were capable of explaining all the others, but of incorporating it – along with the economic, cultural, social and political dimensions – in the search for an increasingly broader approach. and inclusive of historical research. (PÁDUA, 2010, p. 94).

Rodrigues (1997) points out that one of the ways to deal with urban environmental issues is to study concrete forms of development, such as, for example, filling up rivers, felling trees and waterproofing land. Such interventions cannot be thought of only as final consumption, but based on original causes.

Despite a still quite recent discussion regarding the human trajectory, we can say that environmental relations were already present, being perceived or not in each historical period. Therefore, it is not about projecting categories of the present into the past, but using these categories to think about past societies in the course of current problems (PÁDUA, 2010).

In understanding specific issues that affect a given territory, the cartography of each era contributes by outlining the landmarks of the city's spatial transformations, giving us information about what already existed and was important in that period to be recorded and documented on maps (VASCONCELOS, 2009). According to Varela (2008) apud Kanán (2012, p. 13), Historical Cartography can be understood as

The science that studies human events through their representation in the theater of operations where they took place, or their expression in comprehensible schemes, in the case of maps, literary portraits, paintings or schemes, which using images or signs reseña una succesful reality.

For Teixeira (2016, p. 103),

A careful reading of historical cartography, from different eras, articulated with the observation of the city today, allows us to understand the evolution of urban forms and their main characteristics, revealing the conditions that determined the logic of location and implantation, the layout of streets, the location and orientation of squares, the location of functions, the implantation of buildings, as well as the interweaving of the processes that gave rise to these urban spaces.

Historical Cartography constitutes a set of procedures by which the geographic circumstances of the past are reconstructed (NOVAES; PALACIOS, 2015). The combined use of documentary, iconographic/cartographic sources becomes decisive for the understanding of past and current facts, due to the comparisons, analogies and parallels drawn between the present and the past, above all, in the interface cartography and urban environmental issues (ANDRADE, 2013).

Based on the premise that "the map does not constitute the territory, but its reproduced image (created and constructed in memory) and, therefore, is on the map where that vision of space materializes"(KANÁN, 2012, p. 34), the cartographic map should be considered a text that raises questions and allows reconstructions.

From this perspective, there are different ways of translating cartographic images as cultural representations loaded with messages (HARLEY, 1991). This requires specific space-time studies to understand the role of each cartographic "discourse" and its effects on society, since urban cartography is produced as an idea, a record of memory, a historical narrative of geography and landscape. They reveal the identity of the urban space and its changes (FIALHO, 2007). Therefore,

Over time, city maps showed their streets, their buildings, churches, bridges, their comprehensive space, their geographic and political boundaries. Their urban cultures were thus modeled, formatted by the way space was organized. And it was cartography, as a grammar of space, that ordered, classified, normalized and organized the urban space, according to historically defined cartographic regulations, that is, according to the dominant rules in a given time and place. (FIALHO, 2007, s/p).

In short, Historical Cartography provides us with elements to think about the society-nature relationship over time. The transformations resulting from this relationship in a given spatio-temporal context help us to understand ongoing environmental issues, their connections with the past, their present developments and possible solutions that can be taken for a more sustainable future.

THE TERRITORIAL "DISES" OF MOSSOROENSE URBE: DIALOGUE WITH PAST CARTOGRAPHIC PRODUCTS

Faced with representations of the urban space of Mossoro, the first environmental issue associated with the region is inherent to its own geographic location (Map 1), since, forged in the semi-arid region, rainfall irregularity is the main hostile element that influences and

conditions its spatial organization. The climate plays an active role in shaping what we call local urban "diseases", above all, in the occurrence of floods, droughts and droughts that have had an impact on societies since the beginning.

Map 1– Location of the city of Mossoró/RN

Source: Elaborated by the author based on the cartographic base of IBGE (2022)

The city of Mossoró, located in the West Potiguar Mesoregion, is linked to the existence of water bodies and livestock activity, like most cities in the backlands (FELIPE, 2001). Its foundation dates back to 1772, when landowner Antônio de Souza Machado acquired a piece of land on the banks of the Apodi-Mossoró river (Figure 1), "located very close to the left bank of the Mossoró river, and, at the same time, to the forest, with a lagoon between it and the river, as well as drinking water" (SOUZA, 2010, p. 8).

Figure 1 – Plan of the city of Mossoró, 1879, prepared by inspector Gustavo LG Dodt

Source: Teixeira (2009, p. 532)

When we make a comparative analysis of the territorial configuration of Mossoró between the periods of 1883 and 1926 (Figure 3), we observe a progressive densification of the built area around the Mossoró river. Phenomenon that, associated with anthropic interventions, defines one of the most recurrent environmental problems in the municipality, floods in rainy seasons due to an inefficient drainage system.

Figure 3 – Representations of the territorial configuration of Mossoró elaborated by Raimundo Nonato da Silva (1883) and Francisco Alves Maia (1926)

Source: Pinheiro (2016, p. 205; 209)

The first records of floods in Mossoró date back to 1875. Events that occur when water from rivers, streams or storm sewers leave the drainage bed due to the lack of transport capacity of one of these systems, and occupy areas where the population uses for housing, transportation, recreation, commerce, industry, among others (TUCCI; BERTONI, 2003).

The problems caused by floods are strongly correlated to a historical position of arrogance on the part of society regarding the 'natural' dynamics of the watershed, but also of 'innocence' or inadvertence with regard to the

occupation of riverbanks by marginalized populations ('marginal', both from the point of view of housing location and from the socioeconomic point of view) of urban-industrial society. (ALMEIDA, 2010 p. 132).

In addition to the problem of floods resulting from the densification of occupation of Mossoroense territory on the banks of the Apodi-Mossoró river, the cemetery, which we can already visualize in the representations of 1879 and 1883, brings to light the risk of contamination of surface and underground waters by microorganisms and highly polluting substances released during the process of decomposition of corpses (necroleach).

In 1863 [...], the missionary Capuxinho Frei Agostinho marked the same, a piece of land, [...] at Rua do Campo Santo, to build a cemetery on it, bringing together some materials. Recognizing later, however, Vicar Rodrigues, that this land was not suitable for the intended purpose, in 1869 with the help of the people built a wooden cemetery, higher up than that place on high ground, flat and very dry. [...]. (SOUZA, 2010, p. 18).

Thus, we observed that despite the lack of norms and environmental studies on the impacts of the location of cemeteries, there was already a concern with the “ideal” location for the implantation of such equipment. The procedures for the construction of the first necropolis in Mossoró began in 1858, ending in 1869 with the inauguration of the city's public cemetery, located near the Capela Santa Luzia (current Igreja Matriz).

Another problem inherent to the process of urban expansion of the city was the gradual disappearance of many of the existing water courses and lakes in the municipality as a result of its pluvial/underground channeling. At this juncture, Cascudo (2010) reports that there was a drinkable pond near the street that was later called Rua da Alagoa, landfilled during the drought of 1877-78.

In the 1953 plan, prepared by the Saturnino de Brito Office, we can observe mentions of small lakes that currently do not exist (Figure 4). These areas, former riverbeds, are currently occupied by various constructions, constituting recurrent flooding points in the municipality, "roughness" (SANTOS, 2012) associated with a historically persistent problem.

Figure 4 – Plan of Mossoró from 1953 prepared by the Saturnino de Brito Office

Source: Collection of the History of the City, Territory and Urbanism Research Group (2022)

The urban and territorial expansion of Mossoró, in the midst of the climatic adversities characteristic of the region, did not prevent the development of agricultural activity, nor the promotion of the municipality as a center for exporting production. However, this insertion in the international division of labor brought about changes that influenced the emergence of the environmental problem related to water irregularity. This process that results in the "territorial division of labor" translates the dynamic that "creates a hierarchy between places and redefines the ability of people, firms and institutions to act" (SANTOS, 2012, p. 108).

One of the main consequences of the integration of Mossoró into the regional economy was the opening of a new route for the Apodi-Mossoró river in order to reduce the distance from Areia Branca, which caused a change in its fluvial morphology (ROCHA, 2015). According to Souza (2010, p. 44-46),

The river Mossoró [Old Apodi] rises in the foothills of the Serra de Luiz Gomes, crosses the municipalities of Pau dos Ferros, Portalegre, Martins, Apodi, Mossoró and Areia Branca and flows into the Atlantic Ocean, having several rivers and streams as tributaries. [...]. In the drought of 1877 to 1879, at the expense of government aid, the 'new river' was opened, near Porto and Furadinho near Lugar Remanso, shortening the river with these openings, a lot of difference for less, close to 3 leagues.

Other important landmarks for urban expansion and for the emergence of environmental problems in the municipality were: the construction of the railroad, which modified the spatial arrangement of the city, and the construction of submersible dams in the bed of the Apodi-Mossoró river within the urban perimeter of Mossoro. Oliveira (2011, p. 28) reports that:

Its purpose was to guarantee the supply of the growing population and, therefore, the Saco dam, the first source of local supply, located just over two kilometers from the city, was already insufficient. The retention of rainwater, with these dams in the urban stretch predominantly, made access to water possible for many uses, such as the disposal of industrial waste that was installed near the river channel to take advantage of the topographic difference. This transformation happened because, until the period of the commercial emporium, the movement of barges taking and bringing goods from Porto Franco was common, made possible by the movement of the tides that made the water approach the city in its floods, in a flow upstream.

Thus, at the time of the implementation of the railroad, the Apodi-Mossoró river had already been perpetuated and five dams had been built, namely: Barrocas, Cidade, Saco (Genésio), Absente and Ingá. In 1917, the Pedrinhas dam (Passagem de Pedra) was completed, built to prevent the riverbed from drying up as in 1905 (FELIPE, 2001).

The dams were built by the Italian engineer, based in Brazil, Pedro Ciarlini, and currently only four remain. The Barrocas, which is located in the neighborhood of the same name, the Cidade, which, as the toponymy itself indicates, is located in the center of the city of Mossoró, the Genésio, located upstream of the city under the BR-304 bridge and the Pedras, downstream of the city, in the rural area of Mossoró (SOUZA, 2010) (Figure 5).

Figure 5 - Location of existing dams in the urban perimeter of Mossoró

Source: Prepared by the author based on a *Google Earth image* (2022)

As a consequence of the dams built along the bed of the Apodi-Mossoró river, the port of Santo Antônio (with a river bottom) and the Saco dam, which at the time supplied the city, "died" (FELIPE, 2001). However, despite the river not drying up again, the quality of the dammed water did not meet the drinking conditions, due to changes in its physical and chemical characteristics that require time to return to equilibrium.

According to Felipe (2001), the construction of the dams had an economic motivation, since the establishment of a new economic specialization, based on agroindustries, imposed a reorganization of space and social relations. Thus, at the same time that it supplied the municipality, the works served for the industry to throw its waste into the riverbed, inaugurating a new environmental problem in which the "Mossoró River [became] a receptacle for sewage, waste solids and effluents in general" (ROCHA, 2015, p. 122).

The territorial and population expansion of the city of Mossoro, which in 1852 had a population of around 6,000 inhabitants, rising to 7,748 in 1873 (Table 1), demonstrates the pressure exerted on its main body of water, since the sanitary solutions consisted of capturing water for urban supply in the upstream watercourses, with sewage collected and released downstream of the agglomerations, without treatment.

Table 1- Population estimate of Mossoró between 1810 and 2020.

mossoroense population			
Year	Population/inhab.	Year	Population/inhab.
1810	between 200 and 300	1950	40,681
1852	6,000	1960	50,690
1862	2,493	1970	79,302
1873	7.748	1980	145,989
1885	12,000	1991	192,267
1917	16,000	2000	213,845
1922	20,300	2010	259,815
1940	31,874	2020	300,618

Source: Felipe (2001); Cascudo (2010); Oliveira (2017) and IBGE (2022)

Rainwater, as well as sewage, was drained from the urban space as quickly as possible towards water bodies. The main objective of this form of planning was to prevent the spread of

disease. This strategy worked because the cities had a small scale and were far from each other, so that the water bodies, when receiving the sewage, were able to carry out self-purification of the released waste, avoiding the contamination of other cities (TUCCI, 2006) .

The first interventions in the sense of minimizing the effects of flooding in the Apodi-Mossoró river date back to 1976. However, the dichotomization of that river was not able to solve the problem of flooding in the municipality, aggravating the associated environmental and economic damage. A new intervention was necessary to correct the mistake made, with its trichotomization, and the momentary solution of the problem.

After carrying out this work, there was a long period of drought and the absence of torrential rains. However, with the precipitation, the problem reappears in other parts of the city, due to the negligence of the public power in supporting the needy population who end up building in areas of natural drainage of rainwater. A fact that, together with the increasing waterproofing of streets and the existence of obstructed galleries, created other forms of flooding, independent of the traditional floods of Rio.

In 2021, the Public Ministry of the State of Rio Grande do Norte filed a lawsuit against the Institute for Economic Development and the Environment - IDEMA, the municipality of Mossoró and the State of Rio Grande do Norte regarding precarious dams in Mossoró. According to information contained in the file,

These dams are characterized as wet earth passages, breaking every rainy season. [...] The deposition of materials on the riverbed, with the consequent change in the water flow, and in the water course itself, are facts of environmental degradation. [Having] a correlation between the construction of precarious dams, which do not allow adequate water flow and lead to the deposition of material in the river channel, and the floods that have been witnessed in Mossoró and municipalities in the region (STATE OF RIO GRANDE DO NORTE, 2021, p. 1-2).

The State Public Prosecutor's Office, instructed with technical reports prepared by IDEMA and other competent bodies, verified the need to protect the environment against the damage caused by repeated damming works. In short, it appears that the interventions in the Apodi-Mossoró river, especially after the 1985 floods, with the construction of secondary channels, reduced the impact of the waters in the center of Mossoró and in neighborhoods such as Alto da conceição, Centro and Ilha of Santa Luzia, but the "drainage" effect provided by the trichotomization of the riverbed has already been almost annulled by the action of poorly planned/executed works.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The society-nature relationship has undergone numerous transformations over the centuries, with repercussions on the way man relates to the environment in which he lives. The environmental issue permeates the very history of human occupation, with Historical Geography associated with Environmental History helping to understand the positive and negative impacts of this relationship.

When we think about the conformation of the city of Mossoró, consumption and water supply have always been central to its environmental problem. However, past graphic representations of this territory show the expansion of its urban fabric around the Apodi-Mossoró river with developments that go beyond this dimension. The city suffers, since its foundation, from the occurrence of floods, flash floods and floods in rainy seasons, due to an inefficient drainage system.

This conjuncture is related, above all, to a change of anthropic origin in the fluvial morphology of the Mossoró River, with the consequent disappearance of many of the intermittent water bodies due to the construction of pluvial/underground channels. In addition, the waterproofing of the city and works for urban planning made the Mossoró river a receptacle for sewage, solid waste and effluents in general, especially from nearby industries.

Faced with the interventions carried out by the Public Power on the Apodi-Mossoró river, aiming to minimize the effects of floods and recurrent floods in the municipality, the population, without the necessary guidance allied to the lack of inspection by the competent public bodies, started to build along the river bed driven by the false sense of security provided by the years of drought. A series of negative environmental impacts, such as the compaction of its banks and the increase in the devastation of its riparian forest, began to be observed.

In short, the population increase associated with uncontrolled urban expansion, due to the inefficiency of Organs competent municipal bodies in fulfilling their functions, such as the City Hall of Mossoró, which regulates the urban space through the Master Plan and the Code of Works, Postures and Buildings of the municipality, was responsible for transforming spaces that served to drain water into built-up areas. Since the founding of the city, the Apodi-Mossoró river has been silting up. Its banks and canals were partially embanked or leveled due to the lack of drainage services. A reflection of efforts to transform, reform and adapt nature to meet human needs, which endangers the existence of the aforementioned water body, but also the sustainability of the Mossoroense urban environment.

In this sense, the research points out developments for future studies that deal with the consequences of technical solutions directed to the water problem in the emergence of territorial "illnesses" in this cutout on screen, deepening the discussion initiated in the present work.

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